

Localized Versus Time and Space Related Equilibrium

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 14, 2023

Classical statistical equilibrium, for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas for example, is based on localizing the gas to a certain volume and having no average changes in time. In other words, maximization of entropy subject to the average energy constraint $\sum e_i P(e_i)$ is linked with these two ideas. E_i (kinetic energy for no $V(x)$) is a conserved quantity in reactions and overall energy represents a quantity which does not change in time consistent with a center-of-mass which does not change and average values which do not change in time. This approach is associated with a specific kind of statistics, namely that of the constituents of the system. As a result, one obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $\exp(-e_i/T)$ where e_i is an extensive property of a particle (or subset of the system) and T an intensive property linked with the whole system. Entire systems, however, may interact. For example, a N particle system with T_1 may achieve equilibrium with a N system with T_2 yielding a new average $(T_1+T_2)/2$. The probabilities $\exp(-e_i/T)$, however, are for subcomponents of a system.

One could argue that momentum is an additive (vector) quantity which is conserved in collisions, but the average momentum of the system is 0 which does not allow one to describe increases in average p and $-p$ which may be described using energy, i.e. through T temperature.

This begs the question whether momentum may be associated with maximization of entropy subject to a constraint. In (1), we argued that there were flow probabilities in quantum mechanics linked with $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$, which may be obtained formally through maximization of entropy. Here we argue that while an MB gas describes a localized volume with average values not changing in time, x and t state values change, even if p and $pp/2m$ remain constant for a free particle and it may be possible to have a maximum entropy situation to describe the combination of px and $-Et$.

In other words, we suggest localized versus nonlocalized equilibria. The latter represents a quantum free particle, but one may then try to localize such a particle in a potential. What happens in such a case? One does not switch to a localized maximization of entropy as in the MB gas case, because it is possible to have the potential leave the flow unbroken as argued in (1). In other words, the nonlocalized free particle equilibrium is akin to a particle bouncing back and forth in a box, which in classical mechanics is not considered a statistical process. Here we suggest that the underlying picture is statistical meaning that the classical mechanics approach seems to be an approximation. We consider both a quantum particle trapped in an infinite potential well and the ground state of an oscillator to examine ideas of maximizing entropy beyond $\exp(ipx)$.

A key common feature of both types of equilibrium is the product rule $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j)$ or $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x)$. We consider this feature as well.

Classical Localized Equilibrium

A classical Maxwell-Boltzmann gas exists in a localized volume and averages are said to be constant in time. In fact, in some texts the lack of change in time is considered to be a key feature of equilibrium (and the basis of reaction balance it seems). As a result, this is an

equilibrium which does not require the notion of time explicitly nor space x if there is no $V(x)$ present.

A key feature of classical statistical mechanics is that $P(e_i)$, where e_i is kinetic energy (no $V(x)$), may be obtained by maximizing entropy subject to a constraint. We have argued in the past that this constraint is special, i.e.

- (A) It must be linked to a conserved quantity in a reaction, e.g. e_i in a reaction.
- (B) It must be associated with an overall average value which may characterize the whole system, e.g. an MB gas has a total energy which may be approximated by an overall average energy.

(A) might give the sense that e_i is strictly a property of a specific particle, but e_i is additive, so one may consider e_1+e_2 . This begs the question: What is $P(e_1)P(e_2)$ compared to $P(e_1+e_2)$? (B) indicates that one is interested in an overall property of the whole system, so $P(e_1+e_2)$ is the distribution of a piece of that additive conserved quantity and should not depend on this necessarily being linked with a single particle. Thus:

$$P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_1+e_2) \quad ((1))$$

We consider ((1)) to be a fundamental property. The Maxwell-Boltzmann factor follows immediately from it by considering that $P(e_1)$ carries no more information than e_1 and the average energy of the whole system (linked to average pressure per particle) i.e. temperature. In other words, $P(e)$ may describe the probability of an average energy of several particles. We note that the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor describes probabilities for subsets of the system, not the whole system itself, i.e. $\exp(-e_i/T)$. E_i is extensive while T is intensive. One may have interactions between whole systems, but $\exp(-e_i/T)$ describes interactions within the system.

The Question of Momentum

One might ask: Why was momentum not used to obtain an MB factor? Momentum is additive (as a vector) and conserved in reactions, but the average momentum of an MB gas is 0. Thus momentum may not be linked to a total statistical quantity in a gas. If the gas has temperature T_1 it has an average momentum of 0. If it has T_2 , it has an average momentum of 0. Total average momentum does not capture the statistics of the problem, whereas e_i and T do. This immediately begs the question: Does this mean that momentum cannot be associated with equilibrium or maximization subject to a constraint? We argue that it can, but it is linked with a flow type of equilibrium which is necessarily linked with space and time. There exists a very different type of equilibrium, namely that of a quantum free particle.

Quantum Free Particle

A classical mechanical gas is not associated with t or x values, but rather e values, T temperature, density, pressure etc. A free particle is associated with x, t, p and $pp/2m$. It is not interacting, but the postulates (A) and (B) do not necessarily require an interaction for

maximization of entropy subject to a constraint. A free particle is not confined to a region of space and its time and x are changing, so it is associated with a very different kind of equilibrium.

A free particle has a constant p , $pp/2m$ and velocity v . We argue that like the e_i case, one wishes to use a variable which is conserved and associated with reactions. Velocity is not conserved and not associated with impulse hits in the sense that $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$. We suggest that from the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, E is associated with changing time and p with changing x . Even if one did not know about $-Et+px$, a particle at rest at $x=0$ with a running time, would have a momentum and changing x as seen in a frame moving with constant v . Thus p and x seem to be associated and E and t . Instead of having only one variable e_i as in the MB case for which x and t do not change, one may link $-Et$ and px because they are associated through special relativity. One may then create two maximization of entropy schemes:

Maximize $-P(t)\ln(P(t))$ subject to $-iEt P(t)$ to obtain $\exp(-iEt)$ ((2a))

Maximize $-P(x)\ln(P(x))$ subject to $i px P(x)$ to obtain $\exp(ipx)$ ((2b))

The x and t indicate that these values change unlike the classical equilibrium case. "i" is used to make the probabilities periodic, i.e. flow probabilities. One might ask: Why not treat p, E, x and t as deterministic as done in classical mechanics and bypass probability altogether. We address this in the last section before the conclusion.

For ((2a)) and ((2b)), the fundamental feature of the classical statistical mechanical system remains namely:

$$\exp(-iE_1t)\exp(-iE_2t) = \exp(-i(E_1+E_2)t) \quad \text{and} \quad \exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((3))$$

Considering the classical MB gas and reaction balance $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)P(e_4)$, one might think that the property $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_1+e_2)$ follows from keeping the system balanced in time. ((3)), however, indicates that this is not the case. Rather it seems to be linked with distribution of the statistical quantity. A quantum bound state with average energy E is described by $\exp(-iEt)$. If the single bound particle were knocked out of the bound state with a momentum p , it would be described by $\exp(-ipp^2/m t)$. One should be aware that E and p may be associated with average values. For example, a particle with an overall momentum p , may have composite pieces with different momenta yielding average which is taken to be the momentum of the particle-system. As a result, it seems one must be careful in interpreting the meaning of momentum or energy used in a statistical context.

We note that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ describe the entire particle-system and that E, t, x and p are all extensive. This allows these probabilities to be used for interactions with n -slit systems, $V(x)$ potentials, V_1-V_2 sharp potential interfaces etc. A new equilibrium is not established like in the Maxwell-Boltzmann gas with a parameter T , but rather a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s results.

Bound State Considerations

$\exp(ipx)$ describes a free particle system which may interact with potentials. In such a case, a new equilibrium based on extremization of entropy subject to a constraint does not occur. Rather different $\exp(ipx)$ s are created and these interfere. $\exp(ipx)$ is a flow probability and in a number of problems, flow is not broken.. For example, an n-slit interference-diffraction problem may be thought of as a steady state flow problem. There is no equilibration needed to localize the particle. Similarly, a particle may move in one direction with E, p_1 in a region with a constant potential V_1 and then suddenly at $x=0$ change into a region with constant V_2 such that E remains constant and p_1 becomes p_2 with a reflected component $-p$ as well. These are flow problems which are handled by $\exp(ipx)$.

What about interactions with $V(x)$? These may be considered to lead to $\exp(ipx)$ collisions with $V(x)$ which create a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s. This is still a flow scenario as the particle is not fully localized (i.e. There is probability outside the classical turning points, except in the infinite square well potential case). As a result, one uses $\exp(ipx)$ s to create an average kinetic energy which is added to a potential energy to create a constant E at all i.e. the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

Does Any Additional Maximization of Entropy Occur Beyond $\exp(ipx)$?

$\exp(ipx)$ is based on a maxent procedure. Is it possible to have a bound $\exp(ipx)$ system exhibit another type of maximization of entropy? We consider two examples. The first is the infinite potential well and the second, the ground state oscillator.

The infinite potential well problem may be solved by using a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s to form a wavefunction $W(x)$ such that $W(x=0)=W(x=L)=0$ where $0, L$ are the edges of the well. In such a case, it appears that no extra maximization of entropy occurs. One solves this problem in the usual time-independent Schrodinger equation manner. We ask, however, that for a given set of $\exp(ipx)$ s and the boundary condition at $x=0, L$, why would one not expect a statistical approach to assigning the weights of the $\exp(ipx)$ s? For example, one might think that each $\sin(px)$ which satisfies the boundary conditions should have equal weight. Equal weight is consistent with maximization of entropy subject to the constraint $\sum P(i) = 1$. This, however, seems to be a classical approach for which each x point is treated as carrying equal weight. A given $\sin(px)$ treats different x points differently. Even though there is no potential $V(x)$ in $[0, L]$ this does not mean that all x points have the same status. In other words, each px seems to have a kind of equivalency in that $x=\text{constant}/p$ yields $px=1$. Different p, x values arise from viewing the particle from different frames moving with different constant velocities, but the interval L would need to change too as seen from different frames and it doesn't. Thus the different px 's are not equivalent, i.e should not receive equal weights.

Given that we argued that p (momentum) is an average momentum of a free particle-system, one might consider an average momentum for the square well-potential region $[0, L]$. In such a case, the arguments made in this note, suggest one may maximize entropy within $[0, L]$ according to:

Maximize $-P(x) \ln(P(x))$ subject to $\int_0^L P(x) dx = 1$ ((4))

This yields $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ which combine to create a $\sin(px)$ solution based on maximization of entropy. This solution must be identical to the solution of the time-independent Schrodinger equation. Thus maximization of entropy for the whole system does appear in this problem, but this means that weights of individual $\exp(ipx)$ which satisfy the boundary conditions are not the same (as in a coin or die toss).

Ground Oscillator Solution

A second example is the ground state of an oscillator. As we argued, $\exp(ipx)$ is used for flow problems, like a bound problem. The oscillator problem is special in that average kinetic energy equals average potential energy due to p^2/m and $k/2 x^2$ being of the same form. As a result, one may create a wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. In general, $a(p)$ s are fixed through the time-independent Schrodinger equation and not through maximization of entropy subject to a constraint. The statement that the average kinetic energy is the same as the average potential energy is:

$$\sum_p a(p)a(p) p^2/m = E/2 \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_x W(x)W(x) k/2 x^2 = E/2 \quad ((5b))$$

((5a)) is the usual constraint of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas with $a(p)a(p)=P(p)$. There could be many solutions, but if one thinks of the weights (squared) $a(p)a(p)$ statistically and assumes no bias, one might try maximizing entropy subject to the constraint ((5a)). This leads to a Gaussian solution in p for $a(p)a(p)$. How does one know this is the correct solution? $a(p)$ is the Fourier transform of $W(x)$ and a Gaussian represents maximum entropy for the constraint ((5b)), but is also a solution of the time-independent Schrodinger equation. In fact, it is the solution with the least energy. This seems to make sense because higher energy solutions represent flow whereas the ground state represents statistical fluctuations. As a result, the ground state oscillator solution seems to have the same maximization of entropy subject to a kinetic energy constraint as the Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, built in. As a result, a differential equation may actually have maximization subject to a constraint incorporated into its form.

Classical Mechanics

The quantum bound particle in a box seems to be analogous to a classical particle bouncing back and forth in a box. The classical problem is not considered to be statistical. It deals with reflection at the walls such that no energy is lost and considers each x point to be the same. This seems to follow from the idea of constant velocity. There is no sense of maximization of entropy subject to a constraint. There is also no leakage in this or any other classical bound state from the classical turning points as these are bound problems, not flow problems as in quantum mechanics. One may note that for the quantum infinite potential well, as L becomes large, the energy levels are very close and the system is approximately classical if energy is high so that the wavelength is tiny compared with L . The real question seems to be: Why should a free quantum particle be associated with $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and not simply with deterministic E, p, t and x values with $v=x/t$, as in classical physics? It seems that perhaps because there is an

equivalence with a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$, that different frames create p', E', x', t' values, which really represent the same particle. These different frame views must represent a kind of equivalence and we argue that this equivalence is in the phase of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. In other words, $t \rightarrow t + \text{constant}/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + \text{constant}/p$ leave the phase unchanged for any p and E . There is a characteristic time and length which make $-Et+px$ the same (a Lorentz invariant) for each frame. Given that the particle moves in time and space, having a periodic function describes the situation in all of space and time. This leads to the idea of flow, rather than confinement which one finds in both classical mechanics (bound problem) and classical statistical mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a classical statistical mechanical gas is confined to a region of space (volume) with average values which do not change in time. In fact, maximization of entropy subject to an average energy constraint for no $V(x)$, does not use x at all. $\exp(-E_i/T)$ deals with energy probabilities within the system (not necessarily confined to a single particle). E_i is extensive while T is intensive as one does not consider systems interacting (although they can). E_i is used as part of the energy constraint because it is additive, conserved and linked to a total energy which describes the system.

We ask whether one may use momentum instead. It is involved in collisions, additive and conserved, but its overall average value in a gas is zero and cannot describe the whole system statistically. We suggest that for a free particle, however, one does not have confinement in t or x and one may use p and E to describe flow in x and t , still using maximization of entropy subject to periodic constraint $i px P(x)$ and $-iEt P(t)$. These describe the whole free particle system. These probabilities may be used to describe interactions with n -slit systems and potentials. In this note, we consider two special cases, namely a particle in a well with infinite walls and the ground state of an oscillator to see that maximization of entropy subject to a constraint may apply for more than $\exp(ipx)$ in these two cases. In the ground state oscillator case, the Maxwell-Boltzmann type maximization of entropy subject to constant kinetic energy is built-in for the ground state which seems to represent a statistically fluctuating system rather than a flow problem. The symmetry between $pp/2m$ and $.5kxx$ allows one to decouple the average energy from the average potential energy and thus maximize entropy for both in a similar manner to that done for the classical statistical case.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Flow Versus Classical MaxEnt Balance (preprint, zenodo, 2023)